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Fueling Industry 4.0: A professional doctorate in technology

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ABSTRACT

Competitiveness, quality and sustainability critically determine the viability of enterprises on both sides of the Atlantic and around the world. Today's technologically advanced age requires systematic research and development – not the abstract theory-focused research so typical of university, basic and PhD research – but rather the use-inspired, agile and practically-focused research called for in *Pasteur's Quadrant* [1] and more recently the Swiss National Science Foundation [2]. The paper presents a model for a *professional doctorate* program that develops leaders with such skills at the very highest end of this capability spectrum. Such individuals are in demand, particularly by high-tech industries operating at new intersections of technologies. The program is delivered by a hybrid fusion of distance- and campus-based learning technologies and it is focused on enhancing the effectiveness of industry and other enterprises by providing high-performance leaders possessing a significant technological R&D skill set and inclination. The authors see the professional doctorate as essential to any nation seeking to evolve Industry 4.0 [4]. Our concept draws upon the experiences of colleagues in Europe, Australia and in North America and is enhanced by lessons from American entrepreneurship, innovation and distance learning.

Conference Key Areas: 2 • University-Business cooperation
 6 • Open and Online Engineering Education
 8 • Curriculum Development

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INTRODUCTION

This paper presents a work in progress, namely a model for a professional doctoral program designed to meet the current and future needs of contemporary European, North American and Asian business and industry for people with a high level of technology research and development skills and leadership strengths. In particular, the R&D personnel needed to fuel Industry 4.0 are addressed by this program. The paper is organized in three major sections beginning with an Introduction that highlights the core of the need and rationale for the program. Subsequently in section 1 the model for the program is described and in section 2 an implementation plan is presented. The paper's third section shares the authors' conclusions and envisioned next steps.

Clearly competitiveness, efficiency, quality and sustainability are critically important and increasingly interrelated characteristics that determine the future viability of enterprise on both sides of the Atlantic and in fact around the world. These characteristics require systematic research and development – but not the abstract theory-focused research that is so typical of university, basic, and PhD research – but rather the use-inspired, agile and practically-focused research called for in *Pasteur's Quadrant* [1] and more recently the Swiss National Science Foundation [2]. Fraunhofer IAO's Gelec & Wagner [3] noted in particular the increasing need for, and importance of, highly skilled R&D personnel as a major conclusion of their 162 advanced industry study. Clearly these such people will be instrumental in achieving the aspirations associated with Industry 4.0 and, because of their need to understand and have systems level competencies with technology, it is exactly the engineering and technology programs that SEFI encompasses that will have major responsibility in supplying such personnel.

But, where do the people come from who have such skills and inclinations? Particularly those at the very highest end of this capability spectrum? These are the individuals who are most in demand--particularly by high-tech industries -- many of which operate at new intersections of technologies, and/or disciplines, previously thought unrelated.

This paper presents a design for a professional doctorate in technology that will be delivered via a hybrid fusion of distance- and campus- based learning technologies. The program is focused on enhancing the effectiveness of industry, business and other enterprises by providing high-performance leaders armed with a significant technological R&D skill set and motivation to innovate. Importantly, an implementation plan that offers applicability to other institutions around the world is also presented in the paper.

The authors see the professional doctorate as essential to nations seeking to evolve Industry 4.0 [4] because such a doctorate is a flagship strategy for developing the critically needed cohort of technologically capable leaders. Our concept draws upon the experiences of colleagues in Europe, Australia and in North America, enhanced by lessons drawn from American entrepreneurship, innovation and distance learning. For example, Maxwell [5] reported on the rise of this kind of doctoral degree in Australia, New Zealand, England, the Netherlands, and Canada. They encompass disciplines in Business, Design, Technology, Engineering, Industrial Technology, and Engineering Science. In addition, Doctorates of Professional Studies exist in a further variety of fields ranging from Bioethics to Nursing. According to Zusman [6] by 2013 there were

professional practice doctorates in at least a dozen fields in the U.S. with “more than 10,000 degrees awarded just in 2011-12 and roughly 35,000-40,000 students enrolled. (p.1)”

1 WHAT IS A PROFESSIONAL DOCTORATE?

The authors concur with Kot & Hendel [7] that currently, there exists no singular, widely accepted, and formally approved, definition of the professional doctorate. We have, however, noted, based on a synthesis of what European, Australian, and North American thought leaders and early deployers of such programs consider as the core tenets and essential characteristics of professional doctoral programs, that such degrees share enough commonalities to enable formulation of a way forward. In an initial exploration of the concept the authors [8] found that:

Simply put, professional doctorates focus on in-depth, cutting-edge technologies, innovation skills and the leadership and effective organization of teams and corporate units. Such programs seek to prepare advanced level practitioners for business and industry rather than basic researchers for the academy. The goal is enabling increased competitiveness, sustainability and socially responsible endeavor. (p.27).

Insight as to the nature of a professional doctorate can be derived by comparing it to the characteristics of the traditional research-based Ph.D. Table 1 (on the following page) presents a detailed analysis of similarities and differences with respect to 19 key attributes as adapted from Bourner et al. [9]

In addition to the design characteristics highlighted by Bourner, in the American context, it is of critical importance that the Purdue University Polytechnic Institute’s program meets the US Government’s requirement to be recognized as a doctoral level degree. The US Department of Education’s Integrated Postsecondary Education Data System (NCES, n.d.) (IPEDS) classifies “Doctor's degree-professional practice” as follows [10]:

A doctor's degree that is conferred upon completion of a program providing the knowledge and skills for the recognition, credential, or license required for professional practice. The degree is awarded after a period of study such that the total time to the degree, including both pre-professional and professional preparation, equals at least six full-time equivalent academic years.

Because of this requirement, and as depicted in Figure 1, the Polytechnic Institute’s professional doctorate program was designed to build upon a master’s degree and consequently the doctorate is structured to enable completion in 2-3 years or as determined by the student’s intensity of pursuit.

Fig. 1. Duration of a Professional Doctorate

Table 1. Professional vs. Research Doctorates [9] (p.30)

Attribute	Academic Ph.D.	Professional Doctorate
1. Career focus	Entry into academia	Professional doctorates nearly always claim to address the career needs of aspiring professionals
2. Domain of research topic	Disciplinary theory	Professional practice
3. Research type	'original investigation undertaken to gain new knowledge and understanding but not necessarily directed towards any practical aim or application' (p. 71)	Issues of real interest to the profession
4. Research focus	A perceived gap in the literature	A problem encountered in practice
5. Starting point	Finding what is known in the literature	A problem for which the solution is unknown
6. Intended learning outcomes	Contribution to the literature	'A significant original contribution to knowledge of <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • professional practice through research, plus one or more of the following: • personal development (often specifying reflective practice); • professional level knowledge of the broad field of study; • understanding of professionalism in the field; • appreciation of the contribution of research to the work of senior professional practitioners.' (p. 72)
7. Entry qualification & degree	Undergraduate degree with high marks	A Master's degree is often required
8. Experience as admissions requirement	None	1-5 years usually expected, with a median of 3
9. Taught component	Minimal, under the "traditional Ph.D. model"	Ranges from 15 to 50% of degree requirement
10. Modularity	Relatively unstructured according to the "traditional Ph.D." model	Modular course and credit structure
11. In-service vs. Pre-service	Pre-service for research career	In-service for professional career, often taken while working
12. Mode of study	Full-time	Part-time
13. Integration of work/study	N/A	High
14. Integration of practice/theory	Low	High
15. Cohorts	No	Yes
16. Variability of duration	Very high	Low
17. Research outcomes	Long dissertation	Shorter dissertation, often more than one; project reports
18. Assessment	Dissertation driven	Separately assessed components
19. Breadth	Narrowly focused	More broadly focused, problem-driven

Given the findings of the graduate faculty's review of the literature, survey feedback from professional master's degree alumni, and needs assessments, the team worked to create an applied research – use-inspired, technology-focused, professional doctorate. The program is designed to serve an experienced and mature clientele who will demonstrate their proficiency in use-inspired research with an applied dissertation.

1.1 Professional Doctorate Program Design.

The Polytechnic Institute graduate faculty team has formally proposed the creation of a Doctor of Technology graduate degree program to be delivered as a hybrid model

from the Purdue University-West Lafayette campus to active/employed technology professionals. In this proposal, they [11] stated:

This degree program will be distinctly different than the existing Ph.D. in the Polytechnic in multiple ways including the delivery mode, the target clientele, the focus of learning activities, and the research aims of the program. In addition to purposing the degree towards the development of technology and R&D competence needed by business, industry and government, our vision is to employ a hybrid delivery system involving predominantly distance learning education plus some campus-based experiences that make the achievement of a doctoral degree far more accessible to practicing professionals who would not pursue a doctorate or Ph.D. in a traditional campus setting due to their work and home responsibilities.

...

The proposed Doctor of Technology degree is a professional doctorate [12], i.e., a terminal degree, focusing on in-depth understanding of and capability with technology and the concomitantly necessary, innovation and leadership skills of middle and senior leaders in industry, business, and government as well as NGOs. As contrasted to the 'traditional' Doctor of Philosophy's intent to develop *professional researchers*, the professional doctorate is designed to develop *researching professionals in technology* primarily for environments other than the academy. (p.3)

In accordance with the aforementioned design considerations, students in the professional doctorate program will be required to demonstrate the following competencies to graduate:

- Envision, plan and conduct applied research and development activities;
- Identify, comprehend, analyze, evaluate and synthesize research and professional practice;
- Evaluate technologies and technology-related programs and leadership activities;
- Assess individual performance with, and understanding of, technology;
- Communicate effectively and employ constructive professional and interpersonal skills; and
- Function at a high level in one or more of the technology disciplines.

1.2 Target professionals

The Polytechnic envisions that the bulk of the students who will be choosing to pursue the proposed Doctor of Technology will be practitioners from the middle and upper ranks of business and industry, i.e., persons with a documented record of performance and considerable relevant experience. Typically, this is observable by an upwardly directed career trajectory of increasing responsibility. Because the Doctor of Technology focuses on advanced practice, such indicators have more utility for predicting success potential than do standardized examinations.

1.3 Learning experiences & knowledge base

The Doctor in Technology design incorporates best practice instructional and learning technologies to deepen and accelerate learning by employing andragogic approaches and tailoring of the learning experiences to aid aspirants in furthering their education. The outcome will be competencies that can be readily applied in business, industry, government and NGOs, as well as by entrepreneurs, to solve complex technology-

related problems. The proposed curriculum systematically develops enhanced skills and understandings that enable professionals, already holding a Master's degree or equivalent, to apply their heightened technical and conceptual understandings of technology, research and development as they work to develop strategies to advance/enhance their enterprise. Consequently, the Doctor in Technology will accelerate and further the career of such individuals as they contribute to enterprise performance, efficiencies and sustainability through contemporary applied research-based techniques. All students will be required to complete a dissertation focusing on applied/use-inspired research of direct relevance to professional practice.

The program builds upon the particular strengths of Purdue University, and its Polytechnic Institute (the largest technology unit at a Research 1 institution in the nation), by leveraging the national recognition and well established capabilities from existing units including Aviation and Transportation Technology, Computer and Information Technology, Computer Graphics Technology, Construction Management Technology, Engineering Technology and Technology Leadership and Innovation. Given the importance of information to advances in technology, engineering and science the noted strength of Purdue's Potter Library is germane to this point also. Furthermore, other units across the Purdue University Campus also provide a rich environment for the proposed professional doctoral program by enabling supporting/cognate areas of study. These units include, but are not limited to, the Krannert School of Management, and the Colleges of Education, Engineering and Science. [11]

Pursuant to the plan of study, students are required to take:

- 21 credit hours² of core curriculum consisting of:
 - Technology and Society (3 credit hours)
 - History of Science and Technology (3 credit hours)
 - Philosophy of Technology (3 credit hours)
 - Technology Policy and Economics (3 credit hours)
 - The Design Process (3 credit hours)
 - Technology from a Global Perspective (3 credit hours)
 - Technology Clusters and Domains (3 credit hours)
- 15 credit hours for a dissertation is required for the Professional Doctor Technology degree. This will be an applied R&D project focused on a current problem of a company or industry and the results must be defended to the graduate committee.
- 24 credit hours of specialization in any of the technological fields offered by the Polytechnic Institute and by Purdue University. These specializations range from aviation technology, various computer technologies, electrical, mechanical and industrial technologies, as well as technological innovation and leadership.

1.4 Innovative learning and instructional methodologies

The Doctorate of Technology degree program is a predominately distance program with an on-campus weekend face-to-face element; in this sense, it is a distance-hybrid program. Over 50% of the program will be administered through distance modalities. In a typical weekend format, each three-credit hour course will meet for approximately 5-7 face-to-face class hours; three times per semester, for a total of 15-21 seat hours

² A credit hour is the equivalent of 15 person hours of class time plus the attendant amount of homework and independent study

in each semester. Given 15 seat hours per credit hour in a given semester (45 seat hours per 3-credit hour course), that directly implies a distance percentage of 53% to 66% of each course will be provided via distance delivery. This mode of delivery will enable the practitioners to continue to work at their current jobs while taking courses to expand their breadth and depth of knowledge for their specialty.

1.5 Culminating/Capstone research and development experience

All students will be required to complete a dissertation focusing on applied/use-inspired research of direct relevance to professional practice in any of the arenas of today's complex technology-based enterprises. Typically, such dissertations will advance a state of a technology or practice from one Technology Readiness Level to the next higher level. This dissertation must necessarily be defended before the candidate's graduate committee. Note that it is recommended that the graduate committee contain one member from industry with specific expertise relevant to the dissertation topic and not a direct superior in the candidate's employing organization.

2 IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

The team's implementation plan for the proposed doctorate is detailed in the following bulleted steps. The initial steps involve securing the necessary approvals to offer such a degree and then the subsequent ones involve a sequenced process of piloting, revision and enhancement pursuant to continuous improvement and quality control principles.

1. Secure Institutional approval
2. Secure state government approval
3. Announce availability to potential ProSTAR³ clients & recruit first cohort
4. Conduct doctoral faculty and major professor focus sessions
5. Deploy degree planning materials to enrolled cohort
6. Conduct induction training of first cohort students
7. Deliver semester one courses
8. Debrief cohort and faculty members
9. Revise and/or update semester 2 experiences
10. Schedule value-adding experiences
11. Conduct semesters three and four

3 CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

Based on the reviewed literature as presented in this paper's Introduction, the authors concluded, as did the cited colleagues around the world, that a need for a professional doctorate did exist. Furthermore, it was also concluded, based on alumni and potential student surveys, that sufficient interest was manifested to make such a program viable. Pursuant to these two conclusions the author team evolved the program design presented in section 1 and then outlined the implementation steps in section 2. These steps are now underway and approval is being secured as per the outlined sequence.

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³ ProSTAR is the industry facing professional development arm of the Polytechnic Institute

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